

FUZZY TOPSIS FOR THE SELECTION OF DISPERSANT AND FILLER IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTROTECHNICAL COMPOSITES BASED ON POLYSULFONE

Kavaliyova I. N.¹, Dubrovsky V.V.¹, Kavaliyova Y.A.¹,
Ziyamukhamedova U.A.^{2,3}, Podgornaya V.V.¹, Marchenko L.N.^{4,5}, Turgunaliyev E.T.², Elena Torskaya⁶

¹V.A. Belyi Metal-Polymer Research Institute National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Gomel, Belarus

²Tashkent State University of Transport, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

³Kimyo International University in Tashkent, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

⁴Francisk Skorina Gomel State University, Gomel, Belarus

⁵Scientific and Educational Mathematical Center «Sofia Kovalevskaya Northwestern Center for Mathematical Research» in Pskov State University, Pskov, Russia

⁶Ishlinsky Institute for Problems in Mechanics RAS, 119526 Moscow, Russia

Corresponding author: Kavaliyova I. N.¹

Abstract. This study investigates the mechanical and electrotechnical properties of polysulfone-based polymer composites containing varying concentrations of carbon black (soot) and dispersants. An incomplete fractional factorial experiment with a limited and unequal number of observations necessitated an imprecise modeling approach to handle uncertainty. Experimental results were represented using triangular fuzzy numbers. The optimal composite composition was selected using the Fuzzy TOPSIS method. The simulation results identified the optimal soot content for the polysulfone-based composite material, highlighting the significant influence of electrophysical properties on the decision-making process.

Keywords: polysulfone, polymer composites, soot (carbon black), dispersant, Fuzzy TOPSIS

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites that combine different polymers, fillers, and modifiers are widely used in modern technology [1]. Integrating components with distinct properties offers unique opportunities to optimize the characteristics of the final product [2, 3]. This work employs polysulfone (PSU), a thermoplastic polymer renowned for its thermal stability, mechanical strength, and chemical resistance, which finds applications in the aerospace, medical, and electrical industries [4]. To enhance the electrical conductivity of PSU, carbon fillers such as carbon black are introduced. However, high filler loadings without adequate surface functionalization can increase melt viscosity, stiffness, and brittleness while reducing mechanical strength [5, 6]. Incorporating soot into the PSU matrix improves surface electrical conductivity, broadening its potential use in antistatic materials, coatings, electrodes, and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding [7, 8]. Therefore, developing effective modification strategies for polymers like PSU remains a pertinent challenge. This study aims to determine the optimal percentages of dispersant and filler in electrotechnical composites based on polysulfone using a fuzzy logic approach.

2. METHODS

2.1 Materials and Sample Preparation

Polysulfone (PSU) UDEL P3500 (Solvay S.A., Belgium) served as the base polymer. The filler was carbon black (soot) OMCARB (OOO "Omsk carbon", Russia) of grades CH85, T900 (GOST 7885-86), and N339. The dispersants used were epoxidized soybean oil (ESO) ESO-Top (Zhejiang JIAOO Enprotech Stock Co., Ltd, China) and oleic acid (OA) from StanChem (Belgium). The compositions were melt-mixed at 320 °C using a TSSK-35/40 twin-screw extruder. Type 1A samples (GOST 11262-2017) were produced via injection molding on an EN-30 machine (Cheng Heng Industrial Co.).

2.2 Characterization

Mechanical tensile tests were conducted according to GOST 11262-2017 using an AGS-X universal testing machine (Shimadzu Corporation). Impact strength (Charpy method) was measured per GOST 4648-2014 on a PIT 550J pendulum impact tester (Wance). Surface resistivity was determined using a Hiresta-UX MCP-HT800 resistivity meter (Mitsubishi Chemical Analytech Co., Ltd.). The melt flow index (MFI) was measured at 340 °C under a 2.16 kg load using a Ray-Ran MPCA melt flow indexer (Ray-Ran Test Equipment Ltd).

2.3 Output Parameters and Experimental Design

As output parameters (outcomes) - mechanical and electrophysical properties of the polymer composite. The tensile modulus (E , MPa), which characterizes the hardness of the material. In construction materials, increased rigidity improves the performance of the composite. The tensile strength (σ_s , MPa) determines the load that the material withstands without breaking, is a critical parameter for structural materials, the higher the strength, the better. The elongation at break (ϵ , %) characterizes material ductility: higher values indicate reduced brittleness and enhanced impact toughness. For antistatic/conductive materials low surface resistivity (ρ_s , Ω/sq) is required as high resistance - poor electrical conductivity. Also, for electrically conductive composites a low volume resistivity (ρ_v , $\Omega \cdot \text{sm}$) is required. Melt flow rate (MFR, g/10 min) affects material recyclability, high MFR facilitates die casting, extrusion.

The soot regulates the surface electrical conductivity of the material, the experiment was carried out at the following concentrations: T900 - 0%, 13.8%, 20%, N339 - 0%, 13.8%, 18.5%, CH85 - 0%, 4.7%, 5%, 10%, 15%. The addition of ESO in the composite changes the mechanical and electrophysical properties of the polymer, thus affects its strength. ESO concentration was also presented at 4 levels: 0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%. OA is used in polymer composites as a dispersant or plasticizer, it can reduce the fragility of the polymer, increasing its elasticity and toughness. Variations in the addition of soot, ESO and OA help to increase or decrease the strength of polysulfone composite, which can be important when choosing the optimal concentration at which the composite remains stable and has the lowest surface and bulk resistance.

2.4 Fuzzy TOPSIS Methodology

In order to model the uncertainty of the measurements of the resulting features, this study uses symmetric triangular imprecise numbers, where a is the minimum value of three replicates that fixes the lower uncertainty limit, m is the mean value, represents the central trend (core), c is the maximum value that sets the upper bound. This approach effectively describes the variation of measurements due to the heterogeneity of the material or the error of the experiment [6, 7]. The best combination of soot, ESO and OA concentrations in a polymer composite was selected using Fuzzy Topsis. In the general case we have m alternative solutions (combinations of soot concentrations, EMV and oleic acid, ie alternatives), $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m\}$, which is characterized with respect to n criteria C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n (mechanical and electrophysical properties) with triangular fuzzy numbers, $i = 1, \dots, m, j = 1, \dots, n$. The weights of the criteria were determined by the method of entropy, which ensures an objective weighting without subjective assumptions. Criteria C_1 - C_3 were considered as maximization criteria for K_{\max} (benefit criteria), and C_5 and C_6 - as minimization criteria for K_{\min} (cost criteria). For the normalization of triangular fuzzy numbers (TFN) a linear vector normalization adapted for odd numbers was used. [8, 9]. Fuzzy TOPSIS method consists of the following steps. Fuzzy Decision Matrix Construction: A matrix is built with alternatives (A_1, \dots, A_m) as rows and criteria (C_1, \dots, C_n) as columns, using triangular fuzzy numbers as elements. Normalized Decision Matrix: The matrix is normalized to produce elements as triangular fuzzy numbers with a range of [10, 11]. Criteria Weights: Weights for criteria are determined using the entropy method, which assesses data dispersion to assign objective weights, with defuzzification converting fuzzy numbers to crisp values. Weighted Normalized Matrix: The normalized matrix is weighted by multiplying fuzzy numbers by their respective criteria weights. Ideal Solutions: Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS) and Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS) are calculated based on the best and worst criterion values. Distance Calculation: Euclidean distances from each alternative to FPIS and FNIS are computed. Closeness Coefficient: The relative proximity (Closeness Coefficient, CC) of each alternative to the ideal solution is determined. Ranking: Alternatives are ranked in descending order of their CC values.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the variation of input parameters of soot, ESO and OA concentrations, a database of own experimental data from 48 observations was formed. Based on experimental data, the best option should be chosen. Based on this data, we must decide which composition is optimal.

As criteria we consider the mechanical and electrophysical properties of the composite polymer: C_1 – tensile modulus (E , MPa), C_2 – tensile strength (σ_s , MPa), C_3 - elongation at break (ϵ , %), C_4 - surface resistivity (ρ_s , Ω/sq), C_5 - volume resistivity (ρ_v , $\Omega \cdot \text{sm}$), as an alternative any combination of soot, ESO and OA (Table 1).

Table 1. Triangular fuzzy numbers characterizing the criteria C1, ... , C5 for each alternative A1, ... , A13

A_i	Criteria				
	$C_1/ E, MPa$	$C_2/\sigma_s, MPa$	$C_3/ \epsilon, \%$	$C_4/\rho_s, Om/sq$	$C_5/\rho_v, Om-sm$
A ₁	(2,61; 2,64; 2,68)	(71,12; 71,61; 72,19)	(5,79; 5,89; 5,97)	(5,70E+14; 8,57E+14; 1,00E+15)	1,00E+15; 1,00E+15; 1,00E+15
A ₂	(3,01; 3,06; 3,19)	(69,50; 73,82; 76,01)	(3,79; 4,52; 5,12)	(1,50E+14; 3,86E+15; 8,40E+15)	1,40E+14; 1,20E+15; 3,80E+15
A ₃	(3,32; 3,35; 3,37)	(59,37; 63,53; 66,95)	(2,76; 3,06; 3,30)	(1,00E+15; 1,43E+15; 1,90E+15)	1,00E+15; 1,18E+15; 1,70E+15
A ₄	(3,45; 3,52; 3,66)	(47,65; 55,91; 60,51)	(1,92; 2,30; 2,50)	(2,80E+14; 8,20E+14; 1,00E+15)	4,00E+14; 8,50E+14; 1,00E+15
A ₅	(2,91; 2,95; 2,98)	(67,40; 70,15; 73,00)	(3,85; 4,16; 4,47)	(2,60E+13; 4,28E+13; 7,30E+13)	1,00E+15; 1,00E+15; 1,00E+15
A ₆	(3,13; 3,17; 3,24)	(72,19; 73,27; 74,00)	(3,99; 4,24; 4,47)	(5,40E+13; 5,95E+14; 1,60E+15)	1,00E+15; 1,00E+15; 1,00E+15
A ₇	(3,36; 3,44; 3,48)	(64,61; 69,49; 72,20)	(2,94; 3,93; 4,44)	(1,40E+14; 7,10E+14; 1,60E+15)	2,90E+14; 5,45E+14; 1,00E+15
A ₈	(3,78; 3,82; 3,87)	(73,60; 74,63; 75,45)	(3,06; 3,49; 3,87)	(9,00E+14; 2,30E+15; 4,00E+15)	8,00E+13; 1,40E+14; 2,50E+14
A ₉	(3,44; 3,48; 3,53)	(63,09; 64,05; 65,32)	(3,52; 3,57; 3,65)	(3,16E+14; 8,11E+14; 1,36E+15)	2,70E+14; 3,27E+14; 3,67E+14
A ₁₀	(3,60; 3,74; 3,86)	(65,71; 68,48; 71,58)	(3,10; 3,52; 3,76)	(9,00E+10; 3,62E+12; 8,60E+12)	1,40E+10; 4,48E+10; 1,20E+11
A ₁₁	(2,98; 3,03; 3,07)	(53,68; 53,97; 54,34)	(3,21; 3,34; 3,41)	(3,10E+14; 4,18E+14; 5,00E+14)	1,35E+13; 3,71E+14; 8,00E+14
A ₁₂	(2,85; 2,89; 2,93)	(44,17; 44,77; 45,44)	(2,70; 2,77; 2,81)	(2,20E+14; 2,75E+14; 3,20E+14)	6,00E+13; 1,25E+14; 1,80E+14
A ₁₃	(3,15; 3,20; 3,25)	(50,91; 51,51; 52,29)	(2,94; 3,20; 3,25)	(4,80E+13; 5,95E+13; 6,70E+13)	2,50E+13; 4,25E+13; 7,00E+13

In this study, soot concentration ($X_1, \%$), ESO concentration ($X_2, \%$) and OA concentration ($X_3, \%$) were considered as input parameters. The factor X_1 is presented at three levels $X_{1.1}, X_{1.2}, X_{1.3}$. The experiment was carried out with different brands of sows T900 ($X_{1.1}, \%$), N339 ($X_{1.2}, \%$) and CH85 ($X_{1.3}, \%$). (Table 2).

Table 2. Alternative polymer composite compositions

Alternative, A_i	X_1			X_2	X_3
	$X_{1.1}$	$X_{1.2}$	$X_{1.3}$		
A ₁	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
A ₂	0,0%	0,0%	5,0%	0,0%	0,0%
A ₃	0,0%	0,0%	10,0%	0,0%	0,0%
A ₄	0,0%	0,0%	15,0%	0,0%	0,0%
A ₅	0,0%	0,0%	5,0%	2,5%	0,0%
A ₆	0,0%	0,0%	10,0%	5,0%	0,0%
A ₇	0,0%	0,0%	15,0%	7,5%	0,0%
A ₈	0,0%	0,0%	18,5%	7,5%	0,0%
A ₉	0,0%	0,0%	18,5%	0,0%	7,5%
A ₁₀	0,0%	18,5%	0,0%	0,0%	7,5%
A ₁₁	20,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	7,5%
A ₁₂	13,8%	0,0%	4,7%	0,0%	7,5%
A ₁₃	0,0%	13,8%	4,7%	0,0%	7,5%

The normalization of TFN of criteria C_1-C_5 was carried out by formulas (2) and (3). The result is a normalized fuzzy matrix of decisions, $i = 1, \dots, 13, j = 1, \dots, 5$. The membership functions for normalized TFN criteria C_1-C_5 are shown in Figure 1

Fig. 1. Functions of belonging of normalized triangular fuzzy numbers for criteria C_1-C_5 . Each subgraph shows the distribution of values for alternatives A_1-A_{13} with normalized values on the x-axis.

The membership functions for alternatives A_1-A_{13} , derived from triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs), exhibit varying ambiguity based on source data and normalized ranges. For maximization criteria C_1, C_2 , and C_3 , the functions show right-shifted spikes, indicating a preference for higher values, while for minimization criteria C_4 and C_5 , spikes are left-shifted, reflecting a preference for lower values. Alternatives like A_8 display greater unsharpness, suggesting higher data variability. The X-axis range (0 to 1) facilitates visual assessment of normalization and aids in identifying optimal alternatives, corroborated by subsequent ranking via the Closeness Coefficient (CC).

To determine weights for criteria C_1-C_5 , TFNs were defuzzified to obtain crisp center points, enabling the construction of a clear decision matrix. The entropy method was applied to calculate objective weights based on data dispersion, with higher variability indicating greater criterion importance. Table 3 presents the entropy (e_i) and weights (w_i) for each criterion.

Table 3. Entropy and Weights of C_1 – C_5 Criteria

N_0	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5
e_j	0,998	0,996	0,989	0,790	0,862
w_j	0,006	0,012	0,029	0,575	0,379

Criteria C_1 – C_3 exhibit high entropy (>0.98), indicating uniform distribution and low informativity, with weights below 3% reflecting minimal impact. In contrast, C_4 shows the highest informativity ($1 - e_i = 0.21$) and the largest weight (57.5%), driven by significant variability. C_5 , with moderate entropy (0.862), contributes 37.9%, underscoring its influence. Together, C_4 and C_5 account for over 90 % of the total weight, dominating decision-making.

These weights were used to construct a weighted normalized decision matrix. Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS, A^+) and Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS, A^-) were then determined, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Fuzzy Ideal (FPIS) A^+ and Non-Perfect (FNIS) A^- Alternatives

N_0	A^+	A^-
C_1	(0,0054; 0,0054; 0,0055)	(0,0037; 0,0038; 0,0038)
C_2	(0,0114; 0,0116; 0,0118)	(0,0069; 0,0070; 0,0071)
C_3	(0,0283; 0,0287; 0,0291)	(0,0094; 0,0112; 0,0122)
C_4	(0,0000; 0,0002; 0,0006)	(0,0684; 0,2637; 0,5746)
C_5	(0,0000; 0,0000; 0,0000)	(0,0997; 0,1197; 0,3789)

Distances from each alternative A_1 – A_{13} to A^+ and A^- , along with Closeness Coefficient values (CC_i), were calculated and are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Distances to Ideal Alternatives A^+ , A^- and CC_i

N_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7	A_8	A_9	A_{10}	A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{13}
d_i^+	0.158	0.603	0.250	0.152	0.113	0.176	0.149	0.214	0.109	0.013	0.096	0.053	0.027
d_i^-	0.499	0.099	0.403	0.486	0.539	0.477	0.481	0.416	0.523	0.615	0.537	0.577	0.602
CC_i	0.759	0.141	0.617	0.762	0.826	0.730	0.764	0.660	0.828	0.979	0.849	0.916	0.958

The distances and CC_i values reveal significant variability among alternatives. A_{10} exhibits the smallest distance to A^+ (0.013) and the largest to A^- (0.615), yielding the highest CC_{10} (0.979), marking it as the optimal alternative. A_{12} ($CC_i = 0.916$) and A_{13} ($CC_i = 0.958$) also perform strongly, likely due to high saja and ESM concentrations enhancing conductivity. Conversely, A_2 , with the lowest CC_i (0.141), shows the least favorability, attributed to its minimal distance to A^+ (0.099) and maximal to A^- (0.603). Alternatives A_5 , A_9 , and A_{11} (CC_i 0.826–0.849) occupy intermediate positions, reflecting moderate performance.

The dominance of C_4 and C_5 weights (92.4%) suggests that minimization criteria heavily influence rankings, aligning with A_{10} 's optimality despite zero saja and ESM, possibly due to stable mechanical properties. The variability in A_8 's TFNs highlights data uncertainty, which Fuzzy TOPSIS effectively addresses.

4. CONCLUSION

The Fuzzy TOPSIS method effectively processed experimental data with limited observations and uneven design, using triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs) to model variability in mechanical and electrophysical properties. The entropy method determined objective weights, highlighting the dominant role of electrophysical criteria C_4 (weight 57.5%) and C_5 (weight 37.9%), which together account for over 90% of the assessment, while C_1 – C_3 (weights $< 3\%$) showed low informativity due to high entropy. Alternative A_{10} (18.5% N339 soot, 7.5% oleic acid [12,13]) emerged as optimal with the highest Closeness Coefficient ($CC_{10} = 0.979$), attributed to minimal distance to FPIS (0.013) and maximal to FNIS (0.615), driven by balanced electrophysical properties. Competitive alternatives A_{13} ($CC_{13} = 0.958$) and A_{12} ($CC_{12} = 0.916$) also performed well, likely due to high soot and OA content.

Table 6. Alternative Ranks (A_1 – A_{13})

Grades Model	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7	A_8	A_9	A_{10}	A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{13}
TOPSIS	9	13	12	8	6	10	7	11	5	1	4	3	2
Fuzzy TOPSIS	10	13	11	9	5	8	7	12	6	1	4	3	2

Alternatives A_{10} , A_{11} , A_{12} , and A_{13} retained ranks, confirming their consistency, with A_{10} as the leader. Minor shifts (e.g., A_6 from 10 to 8, A_5 from 6 to 5) reflect Fuzzy TOPSIS's better handling of uncertainty, particularly with ESO and OA variations. Compositions with CH85 soot and ESO (e.g., A_2 , $CC_2 = 0.141$) underperformed, favoring N339 with OA for optimal conductivity and mechanical balance.

Fuzzy TOPSIS proved suitable for optimizing multicomponent composites under data uncertainty, recommending A_{10} for electrically conductive polysulfone-based materials. The method's ability to account for electrophysical dominance and OA's dispersing effect enhances ranking reliability, and it more accurately aligns with real conditions and experimental data.

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT.

Kavaliova I.N.: Writing – Original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Correspondent author. **Dubrovsky V.V.:** Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization, Investigation. **Kavaliova Y.A.:** Methodology, Investigation. **Ziyamukhamedova U.A.:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Podgornaya V.V.:** Supervision, Methodology. **Marchenko L.N.:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization, Visualization, Validation. **Turgunaliyev E.T.:** Writing – review & editing. **Elena Torskaya:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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FUTURE SCOPE.

Future research could incorporate additional material properties, such as thermal stability, interfacial adhesion, and long-term environmental aging. Exploring the effects of nano-scale or environmentally benign additives is another promising direction. Integrating the Fuzzy TOPSIS method with other multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) tools, such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), could enhance decision robustness. Experimental validation under real-world operational conditions, coupled with life-cycle assessment and economic feasibility studies, would further strengthen the practical relevance and industrial applicability of the developed composite materials.

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NOMENCLATURE

E : Tensile modulus, MPa.

σ_s : Tensile strength, MPa.

ε : Elongation at break, %.

ρ_s : Surface resistivity, Ω/sq .

ρ_v : Volume resistivity, $\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$.

MFR : Melt flow rate, g/10 min.

PSU : Polysulfone.

ESO : Epoxidized soybean oil.

OA : Oleic acid.

TFN : Triangular fuzzy number.

$FPIS$: Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution.

$FNIS$: Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution.

d_i^+ : Distance of alternative i to FPIS.

d_i^- : Distance of alternative i to FNIS

CC_i : Closeness coefficient for alternative i .

e_j : Entropy alternative i .

w_j : Weight of criterion j .